

Satellite & UAV Data Infrastructure & Applications

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San Sebastian, 17-21.07.2023

CREOTECH INSTRUMENTS MISSION

2

QUANTUM AND TIME SYNCHRONISATION SYSTEMS

SEGMENT SCIENCE

Together with the CERN laboratory, we are implementing the White Rabbit standard for sub-nanosecond time synchronisation - currently in demand in research centres, but the first deployments in telecommunications and energy systems are underway.

Together with Oxford University we are working on the Sinara standard. It allows to assemble control and measurement systems from simple electronic "building blocks", e.g. for quantum computers. Currently, we have implemented into production >30 electronic systems in the Sinara standard.

Estimated CAGR (2017-25): 29.5%
(Persistence)

QUANTUM COMPUTER – EU & PL

SEGMENT SCIENCE

- Creotech is taking part in the Millenion project for the 1000-qbit quantum computer for the EU. The project is executed by the international consortium under the leadership of Innsbruck University and is financed by Horizon Europe Quantum Flagship programme:
 - Phase I (2022-2026) budget is €20 million
 - Phase II (2026-2029) budget is €1 billion
- Another project in this area realised by Creotech is EuroHPC with a total budget of €100 million for 6 countries.

EAGLEEYE

SEGMENT SPACE

- EagleEye product line parameters :
- Flight heritage: mid 2024
- Satellite mass 25-100kg
- Maximum payload mass 50kg
- Available envelope for payload 350x350x400mm
- Design lifetime at LEO 5 years
- Power generation (EOL OAP) (Baseline / Extended) 70W / 200W
- Power available to Payload (EOL OAP) 20W / 150W
- Pointing accuracy APE <math><0.11^\circ</math> (3-sigma)
- AKE <math><0.014^\circ</math> (3-sigma)
- RPE (10s window) <math><0.005^\circ</math> (3σ)
- Slew rate Up to $2^\circ/\text{sec}$
- Propulsion Electric or Chemical propulsion
- Energy storage Up to 500Wh

EXAMPLES OF SATELLITE (AND UAV) DATA APPLICATIONS

SEGMENT SPACE

Agricultural market

Oil reserves

Airports

Car park Monitoring

Mining damages

Activity monitoring

Resolution

Nanosatellite

10m

Mikrosatellite

0,5m

Makrosatellite

0,1m

MORE EXAMPLES OF SATELLITE (AND UAV) DATA APPLICATIONS

SEGMENT SPACE

- Flood monitoring
- Land coverage and biomass assessment
- Soil moisture
- Landslides/vertical ground shifts
- Haze monitoring/fire detection
- Sea pollution monitoring
- AIS / VDES ship monitoring
- Telecommunication towers monitoring
- Terrain profile

CREODIAS

Data and Information Access Services – Copernicus DIAS

- In 2017 consortium led by Creotech Instruments was selected by European Space Agency (ESA) as one of the Copernicus DIAS providers. CREODIAS platform has been put into operations in June 2018

CREODIAS

DIAS Concept

- Standard model of satellite data processing – data downloaded and then processed locally

CREODIAS

DIAS Concept

- Processing brought close to locally stored data

CREODIAS

UAV (drone) Technologies

FMS (Flight Management System)- basic concept

Operating drones transmit their coordinates via trackers to the system providing real-time visulisation and analysis

ADS-B Groundstation – sample use

ADS-B tracking is one of the possible options, along with GSM/Lte based tracking in urban areas

FMS – Flight Management System

View ▾

Call	ICAO	Coordinates	Altitude	Speed	HOT
Dron_1	46F002	[18.54137°, 54.52038°]	40.00 m	10 kn	31.56 m

The system allows for real-time operations monitoring of a fleet of drones and other equipment (e.g. rescue vehicles) equipped with selected trackers (ADS-B and/or GSM/Lte). It can be integrated with UAV flight control systems

Call	ICAO	Coordinates	Altitude	Speed	HOT
Dron_1	48F002	[18.54137°, 54.52038°]	40.00 m	10 kn	31.56 m

The system allows for real-time operations monitoring of a fleet of drones and other equipment (e.g. rescue vehicles) equipped with selected trackers (ADS-B and/or GSM/Lte)

ICAO	Coordinates	Altitude	Speed	HOO
48FF94	[18.52996°, 54.54094°]	50.00 m	15 kn	49.75 m

DRONE RAPID MAPPING - DRM

PORTABLE RUGGED SERVER – ready to be used directly on site, in the field

Up to three displays, optimised for outdoor use in sunlight

Possible to be carried by one person – powerful processing server of suitcase size

Rugged design of the server casing – allowing use in field conditions, directly on emergency incident site

No need to connect to Internet or fixed power supply (possible use of petrol generator or car battery)

Fast multiprocessor server with GPU processing support, Solid State Disks, memory cards reader and WiFi router allowing wired or wireless connection with other terminals

DRM principle of operation

Drone flight

Processing environment

Ortophotomaps

3D Models

DATA PROCESSING AND PRODUCTS:

Results are available shortly after drone data download to the rugged on-site system, orthophotomaps and then 3D models (as needed)

3D MODELS:

The textured 3D models allow for better situational awareness and can easily be shared with rescue team members, other teams or supervisors (also on mobile devices)

MEASUREMENTS:

The field system allows for a set of customised measurements and automated analysis scenarios

GREy

Geomatic Remote EYe

2021

www.grey.aero

GREY services – current status

Terrain height for the selected point

Terrain height statistics within the selected rectangle

Terrain profile for the selected route (fractional line)

Risk map

Topographic objects data/map

Satellite interferometry based monitoring of terrain changes in the selected areas

Analyses examples

Terrain height for the
selected point

Slender objects map

Risk map

Risk map

Extended terrain profile (with graph including information on possible presence of any pre-selected known topographic objects)

SAMPLE

System for Automated Air Obstacles Detection & Monitoring

Introduction

Innovative system for automated detection and monitoring of air obstacles with advanced functions of visualization, risk analysis, reporting and automatic notifications.

Problems to solve

- Air obstacles create serious and obvious threats to air operations safety, especially in the vicinity of airports and have to be monitored very closely
- Airports and air authorities have to meet numerous regulations regarding obstacle management (eg. ICAO Annexes 14 & 15)
- Rapid growth of cities (resulting in emerging skyscrapers, cranes and pylons) determine dynamic changes in their skylines - too fast to be accurately monitored by relevant authorities using standard methods
- Number of UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) operations grows rapidly worldwide, what creates clear need for tools allowing to plan safe flight routes
- More and more different activities require access to reliable Digital Terrain Model source

Obstacles limitation surfaces (ICAO annex 14)

Breakthrough technology

- Analysis done using various sources of Earth Observation data
- The basic set of Input data: **satellite imagery, SAR, Point Clouds** (LiDAR), direct **UAV** measurements, video surveillance
- Output data: **digital terrain model** providing information regarding all objects with the source data resolution
- **Database** provides comprehensive information in numerous formats providing data source for **aviation, telecommunication, construction, agriculture**
- **Machine Learning** and **Artificial Intelligence** used to detect, measure and classify objects

Main scope of SAMPLE

- Accurate, automatically derived information on obstacles in the airfield proximity
- Rapid access to fully reliable data
- Easy obstacle database management
- Low cost data acquisition
- 24/7 availability
- Fully customizable output
- Operational readiness - confirmed by national Air Navigation Service Provider

Obstacles in the airfield proximity

Spatial Portals

High resolution satellite imagery

Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors

HEXAGON
GEOSPATIAL

> Warstwy

=		
=		
=		
	Dane_Katastralne	=
	Rheticus_displacement_PLANET...	=
	GF2_201512111.tif	=
	GF2_201805101.tif	=
	s2a_oper_msi_l1c_tl_epae_2018...	=
	Orto_dron.tif	=
	Model_cieniowany.tif	=
	Open Street Map	=

Cadastral data

The screenshot shows a web-based GIS application interface. The main map area displays a cadastral map with black lines representing parcels and buildings. A red dashed line outlines a specific area, and a blue dashed line highlights a sub-area within it. The background is a green and white map with some text labels like "Park Krajobrazowy Cysterskie Kompozycje Krajobrazowe Rud Wielkich" and "Kopalnia Węgiel Kamienny". The interface includes a map control panel on the left with zoom and pan icons, and a layer control panel on the right titled "Warstwy".

Warstwy	
Granica_haldy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Granica_opracowania	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Natura2000	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dane_Katastralne	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Rheticus_displacement_PLANET...	<input type="checkbox"/>
GF2_201512111.tif	<input type="checkbox"/>
GF2_201805101.tif	<input type="checkbox"/>
s2a_oper_msi_l1c_tl_epae_2018...	<input type="checkbox"/>
Orto_dron.tif	<input type="checkbox"/>
Model_cieniowany.tif	<input type="checkbox"/>
Open Street Map	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Spatial measurements

> Pomiary

Wyczyść pomiary

Wskaż pierwsze miejsce

Wynik pomiarów:

Powierzchnia: 0.589 km²

Model 3D – heap volume calculation

Thank You

July 2023